

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CONCEPTUAL INTEGRATION, MEANING AND UNDERSTANDING

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Abstract

The present paper presents a synopsis of work on language, form, and meaning in conceptual integration theory. It analyzes that conceptual integration and provides a potentially powerful model for explaining a wide range of cognitive processes that build connections among different sorts of ideas. The article concludes that *Conceptual blending* refers to a set of cognitive operations for combining words, images, and ideas in a network of "mental spaces" to create meaning.

Keywords: Conceptual meaning, understanding, integration of meaning, artificial intelligence.

There are two main means of structuring knowledge.

- 1) Conceptualization of knowledge,
- 2) Categorization of knowledge.

Conceptual integration theory (also called conceptual fusion theory) developed by Gilles Fauconnier and Mark Turner (see: 5)) in the late 20th century has played an important role in clarifying many controversial issues in linguistics, including comprehension issues, especially text comprehension, in the investigation of problems that have been waiting for a long time to be solved.

The main essence of this theory is that the cognitive operations that take place in the human brain and combine language and thinking can create different meanings. They range from the simplest meanings and concepts to the most complex theories. But such concepts, which seem simple to us at first glance, are actually not so at all. When we speak, think, or even hear, we do not understand the essence of what complex operations are going on in our brains. [5:43]

It is known that language and thinking are connected to each other through 3 types of visualizations (in J. Fauconnier and M. Turner these are explained as "mappings").

The first is a projection image, the second is a pragmatic-functional image, and the third is a schematic image. It was on the basis of the mental field that the Fauconnier-Turner couple determined the emergence of a unique theory in linguistics - the theory of conceptual integration. The essence of this is that conceptualization is the process of understanding information that leads to the creation of concepts. Today, the main cognitive processes in linguistics are understood under the name of the theory of conceptual integration, which has a certain scheme implemented with different levels of abstraction. This scheme includes the output space (Fauconnier-Turner couple calls it "input spaces") and the blended space ("blended space"). [5:172]

All of these represent the "mental field". All of them (of the mental field) are related to conceptual integration.

Then what can be the role of conceptual integration in people's understanding of each other, comprehensive understanding of the information they read and hear? Because our daily life is colorful, the information received during the day is also colorful and has different genres. In artistic texts, scientific texts, political texts, academic-educational texts, we encounter information in an informative, aesthetic, didactic style, while in informative-advertising texts, we encounter all of these from a pragmatic point of view. The new meaning is created as a result of three mental operations - imagination, integration, similarity - performing a complex task together. The difficulty in studying conceptual integration processes is that these processes exceed the boundaries of our consciousness.

As can be seen from this brief information, the role played by the issue of conceptual integration in the comprehension and understanding of the text is irreplaceable. It is precisely because of this importance that the mentioned issue is addressed from time to time, which determines its relevance.

It is known that reading comprehension, writing comprehension, and listening comprehension play an important role in the educational process. All of these processes are mental processes, in which there is an interactive activity between the person performing the action (reading, writing, listening) and the texts. We fully understand the text when we have various skills-habits - to navigate the text, localize information, to feel the spirit of the text, to reconcile events. A reader or listener without such qualities will not be able to get anything other than a superficial understanding of the text. [1: 216]

By participating in the communication process, we sometimes understand what is being said, and sometimes we create the text-speech ourselves. In the first act, our main goal is to understand the ideas expressed in the language. Language is a means of embodying an idea. However, the knowledge used in language coding is not limited to our knowledge of language. Along with our knowledge about the world, the social context of the text, the ability to communicate the information in the memory, plan and manage the discourse and other

aspects also play an important role here. At this time, none of the available forms of knowledge is more important than the other in the process of understanding. None of them is clearly preferred. Only the study of the means of interaction, the mobilization of all knowledge, helps to understand the essence of language communication and conditions the clarification of the nature of the semantic results realized by language practice in everyday life. [3:218]

The study of knowledge during language communication is studied as one of the main directions of cognitive science. Starting from the mid-70s, "cognitive science" began to be developed as the processes of human gathering, using and assimilating information. It is no coincidence that one of the main issues of psychology found its solution in cognitive psychology: human behavior his niche is determined by his knowledge. Knowledge also plays a crucial role in the artificial intelligence system here. Here, the very concept of intelligence is often related to the ability to "use" the necessary knowledge.

In many studies on artificial intelligence, the main goal of the general theory of language is considered to be the explanation of the mechanism of natural language, the mechanism of its understanding. Undoubtedly, the basis of such a model is the interaction of different types of knowledge, and linguistics no longer has "sole authority" in the development of a general model of language. The development of such a general language model can only be solved within the framework of all cognitive sciences.

Although there are various levels of research dedicated to the study of cognitive language aspects, many issues still remain open.

However, two main problems are more discussed in the researches of recent years.

1. The structure of providing different types of knowledge.

2. Means of conceptual organization of knowledge in the process of understanding and construction of language information. [4:59]

Providing certain knowledge during language communication is a very complex and controversial issue. Explicitly expressed knowledge is only a part of the general knowledge base. The storage of information in this knowledge base is not static, on the contrary, it is a self-creating and self-regulating system that constantly moves and changes based on new information.

The knowledge base is based on at least the following components:

1) Knowledge of language; a) grammar (together with phonetics and phonology), (supplemented with lexical semantics); b) knowledge of language processing rules; v) knowledge of the principles of speech exchange.

2) Foreign language knowledge: a) context and situation, knowledge about the addressee (goals and plans set by the addressee, his perception of the speaker, circumstances; b) general background information (about the world), knowledge about events, situations, actions and processes. [2: 41]

Issues that form the basis of knowledge have been sufficiently explored. The difficulty mainly arises in

clarifying the appropriate structure of the transmission of existing knowledge. For example, what distinguishes the structure intended for the provision of pragmatic information from the structure used for the provision of syntactic information? Or rather, is there a particular level of syntactic representation? What ideas does a person rely on in the process of understanding language?

The order of the waiting list can be extended. For decades, one of the most important results in the theory of cognitive learning has been the idea of the inextricable interaction of the processes occurring in human memory, as well as the clarification of the construction and comprehension of language information. Indeed, the understanding of any new situation leads, first of all, to finding a situation close to it in memory, a little similar to it. In order to analyze and comprehend new information, we have to refer to the previously accumulated experience in our memory. This search is based on the fact that the structure of analyzing and perceiving new information is similar to the structure used to organize memory.

The main importance of past experience in remembering and understanding our information was first researched by F. Bartlett in the 30s of the last century. When he studies the features of understanding texts, he concludes that memory never has a true character. Depending on the social environment, its (text) form often changes in the memory during the re-creation and imagining of texts. He used the concept of "schema" for the purposeful storage of information in memory. By this "schema" he understood the active organization of past experience. [3]

One of the structures for imagining high-level semantic information and the simplest are scenarios. (This is discussed in more detail in A.A. Abdullayev's work entitled "Discourse Analysis and Theme Development". See: A.A. Abdullayev, 2004). A scenario is a set of low-level concepts related to time and cause and effect, which describe the regularization and ordering of stereotyped events over time.

Unlike the theory of artificial thinking, the concept of "frame" rather than the concept of "scenario" is used in linguistics. Ch. Fillmore gave a comprehensive description of the theory of frames and compared the semantics of understanding with the semantics of truth.

With frames, schemes, scenarios, plans, etc. the so-called knowledge structure itself means a package-set of information.[4:159]

This data set is stored in memory, or created as needed from components already present in our memory. It is this set of information that ensures that standard situations fall into a suitable cognitive-thinking form.

These structures play a crucial role in the functioning of natural language. Through them, the relevance of the texts is determined, both at the micro and macro level, and the necessary conclusion is reached; ways of their activation are clarified (eg. etc. some features of giving definiteness - indefiniteness in languages with articles). Finally, they emphasize the importance of context, which allows predicting future events based on structurally similar past events.

"Strategies" are considered to be the best examples of structures intended for imparting pragmatic knowledge. The famous Dutch linguist T. van Dijk, together with B. Kinch, wrote a book called "Strategy for Understanding Related Text" that gives a very good analysis of this issue. The authors emphasize the dynamic aspect of connected text comprehension and write that the comprehension process is strategic in nature. The strategies used in the comprehension of texts are often not pre-programmed, they are beyond the conscious control of the speakers of the language. At the same time, they depend on rapidly changing and cognitive structures (knowledge, plan, instruction, goal). Action strategies are hypothetical and reasonably specific. With their help, the most likely structures are quickly revealed, as well as the importance of receiving the given information. Strategies are also characterized by action on several levels that exist simultaneously, are able to use incomplete information and combine them with inductive and deductive means of analysis.

The authors note that some of the strategies have linguistic features. This includes strategies related to the surface structure of texts during the semantic analysis of texts. Others are mainly about cognitive strategies. The decisive importance for their action is played by the knowledge about the objective entity, the situation and other cognitive information.

Another point of view, which is the exact opposite of the teaching, should be mentioned here. Its supporters believe that knowledge does not play a major role in solving the problems of language analysis. In the event that the analysis process is carried out by specific individuals, then, according to these linguists, features that are not subject to stereotyping and conceptual modeling are of decisive importance. Here, the purposefulness, creation and provision of worldview, hidden (hidden) evidence, emotional states, and needs are understood.

In general, the problems of knowledge organization and the means of their delivery are very closely related to each other within the broader framework of natural language analysis. If the methods of presentation of knowledge have been regularly developed in the works devoted to the problems of artificial thinking in the last two decades, the issues of organization of knowledge have become the focus of attention only in recent years.

In the 80s of the last century, several constructive ideas dedicated to the study of the conceptual organization of knowledge were formed. This includes the assumptions put forward by G. Lakoff and his supporters about the integral nature of language analysis. According to them, the provision of language information is a single - holistic process and takes place simultaneously at all levels of the language - syntactic, semantic and pragmatic. Semantic interpretation is not necessarily required after syntactic analysis. It can be started quickly on the basis of already known information about syntactic structure, and both semantic and pragmatic information can be used during syntactic analysis. [7]

The results of the analysis obtained at any of the language levels are useful for all other levels. There are two possible forms of cross-level relationships. In the first case, the interaction is organized hierarchically. (Unmixed levels interact through intermediate levels). In the second case, "cross-communication" occurs between levels. At this time, each level can be directly connected with all other levels (see: Abdullayev, 1998).

Underlying the ideas of an integral analysis of language is the broader idea of a single level of knowledge transfer. This idea is based on the ability to combine language, sensory and motor information.

We would be wrong if we say that the sum of all the knowledge and ideas available to the speaker and the listener are used during congress speech acts. That's why it is necessary to develop such a conceptual tool that is satisfied with the multitude of existing factors in the interpretation of texts. In this regard, concepts such as "focus" and "relevant" are often mentioned in linguistics literature. (Especially in the works of D. Shperber and D. Wilson, U. Lenart).

M. Minsky suggests applying the system of "cognitive sensors" when talking about the conceptual problems of knowledge. This system prohibits certain forms of speech behavior.

Researches of the famous linguist J. Lakoff cover wider problems in this field. In modern times, a more promising direction, which resonates with the problems of presentation and organization of knowledge, "semantic method" is widespread. Knowledge of dynamic scope is provided here in procedural form rather than in the form of a rulebook. More experts in this kind of research is considered more appropriate for the creation of systems. Here also, as F. Johnson-Laird showed, the means of organizing knowledge in a procedural form also differ.

The cognitive approach to language is such a dynamically developing current that the obtained results are updated quickly. Successful findings obtained during the study of language will undoubtedly be of great importance in the theory and practice of computing systems, machine translation, and search-information systems. However, it should not be forgotten that the study of cognitive aspects of language will only lead to the effective solution of applied tasks, as well as to deepen our understanding of the mysterious mechanisms of language communication. And we are thinking about the problems that have always bothered us for hundreds of years. How should we understand each other better? How accurately and fully does language express our feelings and thoughts? As you can see, we are still far from a complete solution to these or similar problems.

There is a strange proverb: He who knows a lot takes a lot! I wonder why the one who knows so much should take so long. The writer Anar skillfully revealed this in the work "Troule to understand", which tells about the life of Jalil Mammadguluzade. Mirza Jalil, who served his people for many years with his pen, enlightened ideas, and beautiful artistic and publicist works, suffered unimaginable misfortunes! This happened at that time, in the Soviet system. And now, sometimes the "trouble of misunderstanding" is taking place, it makes people nervous and angry. What is this

disease? Why do we not understand, are not understood, or do not want to understand, do not want to understand? When will these reasons decrease?

To conclude, in the epigraph of his novel "Living to Tell", Marquez expresses the idea that, in fact, life is not how one lives, but how one remembers it, but also the ability to tell others. Loneliness, loneliness, and emigration arise from this in all times and in all countries. The main problem of the world: thinking has moved, leading countries seem attractive in this sense and embrace it intelligently.

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THE GENDER APPROACH IN THE CONTEMPORARY LITERATURE

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К ПРОБЛЕМЕ ГЕНДЕРНОГО ПОДХОДА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ

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Abstract

In modern science there is no consensus on the terminology in the field of literature written by women. The article makes an attempt to investigate the relevance of the gender approach to the study of modern literature.

Аннотация

В современной науке не существует консенсуса относительно терминологии в области литературы, написанной женщинами. В настоящей статье предпринимается попытка рассмотреть актуальность гендерного подхода к изучению современной литературы.

Keywords: modern literature, gender approach, gender, woman's literature, self-identification.

Ключевые слова: современная литература, гендерный подход, гендер, женская проза, самоидентификация.

Современная литература - очень сложное и неоднородное явление. Исследователи, говоря об общей ситуации в русской литературе постсоветского периода, фиксируют ситуацию общего культурного кризиса рубежа веков, усугубленного внутренним кризисом, связанным с распадом Советского Союза. Исследователи разделились на тех, кто видел в новом периоде развития литературы признаки упадка, а также на тех, кто считал литературу 1990-х периодом больших экспериментов, свойственные для культуры переходного периода. Дискуссии вызвали также подходы к исследованию нового периода. В попытках типологизировать современную

литературу исследователи этого явления столкнулись с изрядными трудностями. Главным результатом стало то, что попытки систематизировать литературный процесс 1990-х годов с помощью привычных методик: по жанрам, стилям, направлениям и т.д. - давал приблизительную, а подчас искаженную картину, поэтому ученые заговорили о несовершенстве старых методик. Исследователи искали новые подходы к изучению сложных современных литературных явлений. Говорили о том, что на этом этапе необходимо определять общие, доминантные тенденции развития. Предлагалось изучать индивидуальные поэтики авторов в сочетании с традици-